

A Filter Paper based Sensing Element to Detect β -Cyclodextrin in Aqueous and Biological Fluid

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Through all these years cyclodextrins (CDS) have been subjected to extensive studies¹. The wide-spread interest in CDS can be traced to their unique ability to form inclusion complexes with varied components. The industrial applications of CDS particularly in pharmaceutical, food and allied fields have been documented². Several analytical procedures mainly chromatographic methodologies have been suggested to detect and estimate CDS in different matrices³. Surprisingly, a simple device to sense CDS in aqueous or biological matrices has not yet been reported. The present communications reports the development of a simple sensing element to detect β -cyclodextrin (BCD), the prominent member among CDS, in biological medium like urine.

Results and Discussion

It is known that cyclodextrins form stable inclusion complexes with phenolphthalin⁴. As a result, the colour of the alkaline phenolphthalin solution reduces and the extent of reduction in colour can be correlated with the amount of CD. The reported method is based on the disappearance of pink coloured spot from a filter paper strip as a result of interaction with BCD.

The results (Table 1) reveal that 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of BCD can be taken as a detection in water limit while 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in case of urine sample. The time taken to disappear the colour of the spot is less than a minute indicating the rapidity of the method.

Urine contains several components and BCD could form stable complexes with those components. In that sense the concentration of free BCD which can form complex with phenolphthalin would be less than the amount added. The considerable variation between the detection limit of aqueous and urine samples could probably be traced to this aspect. The detection limits are indeed based on the visually observable colour change from pink to colourless. Though we have not attempted, the variation of intensity of the coloured spot due to complexation can be

quantified using reflectance spectroscopic method. In that case the detection limit would be considerably less.

TABLE 1—INTERACTION OF BCD WITH ALKALINE PHENOLPHTHALIN SPOT

Concn. of BCD in water $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Colour of spot	Concn. of BCD in urine $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Colour of spot
100	Disappeared	100	Disappeared
80	Disappeared	80	Disappeared
60	Disappeared	60	Disappeared
40	Disappeared	50	Disappeared
20	Disappeared	40	Intensity reduced
10	Intensity reduced	30	No change

Experimental

β -Cyclodextrin (BCD) (Sigma) was used as such. Phenolphthalin and methanol (chromatographic grade) (both B.D.H.) were used

BCD was dissolved in distilled deionised water and freshly collected human urine to get varied concentrations (100 to 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$). The urine solution was made alkaline by adding few drops of 0.1 N NaOH. A dilute solution of phenolphthalin (0.005 g ml^{-1}) was prepared in methanol-water (1 : 1, v/v) and a few drops of 0.1 N NaOH was added to get an intense pink colour.

The phenolphthalin solution was dropped onto a Whatmann no.1 filter paper strip to get a pink coloured circular spot (1 ± 0.1 cm dia). The filter paper strip was then dried and BCD solution was directly dropped over the spot.

References

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